

**ENHANCING GRADUATE EMPLOYABILITY AND
SOCIAL IMPACT THROUGH&NBSP;CULTURALLY
RESPONSIVE SOCIAL BUSINESS EDUCATION AND
DESIGN THINKING: A GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE**

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Enhancing Graduate Employability and Social Impact Through Culturally Responsive Social Business Education and Design Thinking: A Global Perspective

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Abstract

Social business is becoming more and more important as individuals give it. It is a way to solve social problems and raise recent college graduates' worth. With thorough interviews conducted with individuals from several countries, teaching people about social business might help them land jobs. It underlines the significance of having a strong mind, backing up your business with friends and relatives, and feeling you could succeed. People can choose skills from social businesses that will help them start a profession and help the world to be better. More people might land jobs these days mainly because of the psychological skills and endurance taught in social business programs. Social business should be taught in universities. People might be more fit for business and earlier.

Keywords: *Education, Social Entrepreneurship, Employability, Design Thinking, Global Perspective*

INTRODUCTION

According to Weerawardena and Mort (2006) and Tam et al. (2024), social entrepreneurship is spreading worldwide to address unemployment and social injustice. Social entrepreneurship provides a tool to help undeveloped places blossom. It also helps one get work when traditional routes of employment line up closely. Many in the international business sector also prioritize world transformation and sustainability. This underlines even more our need for social work anchored on businesses. Apart from business objectives, long-term social and economic ones depend on this.

It still needs to be easier for us in this region. The Philippines still needs more graduates of universities with jobs. The demands of companies differ, as well as what education teaches. Particularly in social entrepreneurship, these skills might influence the job market, so teaching young people business skills is becoming increasingly important for institutions. Students studying social business fit more for various tasks in their future work (Lawler, 2018; Maheshwari & Kha, 2021). This is true when their confidence in their competence and flexibility rises.

Though many people know this, fresh studies show that social business has minimal impact on cultures despite its benefits. Earlier research mostly focused on conceptual frameworks (Gregory & Anderson, 2006) or effects occurring solely in one area. When they

originally stumbled onto social business, they hardly looked into what occurred to people in different cultural settings. This study primarily ignores this difference as it mostly concentrates on how successfully social business functions across several countries to help fresh graduates get jobs.

This study is critical as it fully illustrates how social business might help recent college graduates find jobs in different cultural settings. It will help leaders, teachers, and social entrepreneurs develop original ideas to probe the interactions between psychological resilience, self-efficacy, and social support in this process (Baluku et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2022). They will add to the discussion on improving college policies so that graduates might land jobs wherever in the world (Halsall et al., 2022; Yi, 2022).

Research Objectives

1. To investigate how education in social entrepreneurship may support graduate employability to be raised in various cultural settings.
2. To pinpoint the principal elements influencing the link between graduate employment and social entrepreneurship education, particularly perceived support and resilience.
3. To look at how employment in Western and non-Western industries impacts response to social entrepreneurship education.

4. To offer concepts on how to add social entrepreneurship into courses to raise graduate employability.

Statement of the Problem

While social entrepreneurship is becoming increasingly accepted as a way to raise employability, more is needed to understand how this promise is fulfilled in many cultural settings. Little is known about how psychological and environmental elements could change this relationship. To determine the main determinants driving this relationship, this study seeks to close this gap by examining how social entrepreneurship education influences graduate employability in Western and non-Western societies.

Research Questions

1. In what ways may understanding social entrepreneurship affect graduate employability in various cultural settings?
2. Which essential elements link employability with social entrepreneurship education?
3. How differently does education in social entrepreneurship affect employment in Western and non-Western settings?
4. How may social entrepreneurship be included in higher education courses of study to raise employability?

Literature Review

Introduction to Social Entrepreneurship

Combining social entrepreneurship with teaching students how to treat people and think like company owners can help tremendously increase their chances of finding employment after graduation. This two-pronged strategy seeks to satisfy the expanding need for college graduates who can manage the demanding requirements of contemporary business and assist in solving societal problems (Praszkier & Nowak, 2011; Martin & Osberg, 2007). According to studies, children exposed to social entrepreneurship acquire creative, tenacious, and problem-solving abilities. In a world that is fast evolving, these are all abilities required to land a job (Tam et al., 2024; Rahim & Mohtar, 2015). Particularly in employment that emphasizes fresh ideas and doing good for society, social business also makes college graduates more flexible and able to operate in various situations (Peredo & McLean, 2006; Zamry & Sahid, 2021). This is so because social business gives people the sense of a mission to serve others. However, cultural

variations and the requirement of a particular approach considering the social and economic history of the community may influence how effectively social entrepreneurship education works (Urban & Kujinga, 2017; Sullivan Mort et al., 2003). This would make it simpler for recent graduates to land employment, benefiting the economy and society (Maxwell & Armellini, 2019; Wahid et al., 2019). Social entrepreneurship training teaches individuals how to launch their firm and helps them develop critical thinking skills, which are highly sought after in the current workplace (Sullivan Mort et al., 2003; Dees, 2018).

Today's employers desire candidates who can handle complex social issues and advocate ecologically responsible company practices (Spear, 2006; Dacin et al., 2010). When businesses prioritize hands-on learning and real-world application support with their initiatives, social business education also helps students land jobs (Tam et al., 2024; Asici, 2021). These initiatives might be more successful if combined with more extensive university programs, such as working with social firms, community service projects, and diverse teams (Rahim & Mohtar, 2015; Fulton & Dees, 2006). Replicating social business education in several cultural environments maybe difficult due to social concepts. Three primary concepts underpinning social business are innovation, changing the world, and long-term success.

However, their utilization should be determined by the local requirements, beliefs, and financial situation (Urban & Kujinga, 2017; Klarin & Suseno, 2023). In more developed nations, greater emphasis may be paid to merging new social concepts into present economic structures and applying them on a larger scale. Teachers of social entrepreneurship, for instance, would emphasize self-employment and launching modest, long-lasting enterprises addressing local issues in areas with a lot of graduate unemployment (Rahim & Mohtar, 2015; Zamry & Sahid, 2021). This abundance of data supports the notion that social business education must be flexible and fit for certain circumstances. Knowing this will help ensure that it generates more employment and significantly alters society in many other respects. By continuously adjusting these approaches to instruction, universities can let graduates perform successfully in a global economy that is getting more complex and fast-growing (Maxwell & Armellini, 2019; Martin & Osberg, 2007).

Social Entrepreneurship and Employability

Social entrepreneurship could open employment. Most individuals believe that social business should be taught in higher education to increase graduates' employability (Martin & Osberg, 2007; Peredo & McLean, 2006). Apart from addressing social issues, social entrepreneurship imparts knowledge on operating in today's hectic employment environment (Abu-Saifan, 2012). Building in environmentally friendly designs piques the curiosity of more and more individuals. This approach conforms with the global trend of prioritizing social and corporate impact (Peredo & McLean, 2006). Social entrepreneurship might be the solution in countries like Malaysia, where there is an apparent discrepancy between what businesses need and what individuals learn in the classroom. Teaching practical and vital skills for daily life helps one to do this (Rahim & Mohtar, 2015; Wahid et al., 2019). Though geography has excellent potential, most of the current study is concentrated on academic concerns or what the area denotes. This implies that we still have to study more on how to use social business in various educational environments (Sullivan Mort et al., 2003; Urban & Kujinga, 2017). Complete educational programs designed to equip learners for today's demanding job market may be launched if this disparity could be bridged. College students should be taught social business (Dacin et al., 2010; Weerawardena & Mort, 2006).

They are more useful as they demonstrate to them how what they acquire in the classroom applies in real life. College graduates learn differently than businesses expect, making it more difficult to land employment (Rahim & Mohtar, 2015; Wahid et al., 2019). According to Martin and Osberg (2007), social business enables individuals to improve in areas including problem-solving, adaptability, and generating fresh ideas they may apply at their jobs. Children and teenagers wishing to assist with ongoing social projects might pick up these abilities. This benefits them and presents a realistic picture of things (Abu-Saifan, 2012). One may assist others and earn money at the exact moment. It also seeks to serve others and gradually expand globally (Peredo & McLean, 2006). Through these seminars, students will acquire in-demand skills and equip themselves for a competitive job market (Weerawardena & Mort, 2006; Sullivan Mort et al., 2003). Everyone benefits from everyone being more honest and performing better in their work. It transforms programs and results to foster a social business approach. It helps people to think and behave in fresh

ways. This alters the central teaching approach for social business.

Cultural Contexts in Social Entrepreneurship

Social business is widespread in communities and in the ways of life in which it is expressed. Combining these concepts will help influence children's education to improve in social business. Those in the West who study social business nowadays generally focus on free, innovative concepts grounded in the market. Two diverse groups of individuals see great importance in freedom and riches (Sullivan et al., 2003; Kickul & Lyons, 2010). They teach young people many lessons on creativity, uniqueness, and commercial acumen. People from business and support organizations can help realize social business objectives. There are not fewer or appropriate social business-oriented colleges outside the West. Their concerns span individuals, getting things done, and everyone's health and happiness. Many non-Western nations are so expanding as this is their reality. The connection to social business is becoming more and more solid. People are advised to get active in their communities, cooperate to repair problems, and handle social issues to match their personal beliefs and aims (Datta & Gailey, 2012; Ashta et al., 2012). This may teach them more about sound business practices. The social business may be more challenging to learn about in particular areas depending on the policies, social conventions, and support networks in place. These are different from what you would see in the West. Though they could accomplish so in various ways and with different objectives, social business schools might assist locations inside and outside the West. These qualities are appreciated in the West as they enable companies to determine the needs of their consumers. It improves things and gets people thinking creatively (Dees, 2018; Saebi et al., 2019). In a non-Western environment, people can meet others, create organizations, and discover solutions that fit other cultures (Mato-Santiso & ReyGarcía, 2019; Aning, 2022). Someone who exists in the world wants everyone to be content and healthy. It can be more helpful as individuals pick it up differently depending on where they live. Those running for government or those who educate should consider how children from various backgrounds will react to their social business teachings. They can satisfy local needs and use outdated items in this regard. Combining what children acquire in the classroom with real-life activities can help them land employment (Singh et al., 2023; Zamry & Sahid, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This article applied a qualitative research technique to evaluate, in numerous cultural contexts, the impact of social entrepreneurship education on graduate employment. A phenomenological approach helped one understand the participants' lived experiences and the essential components affecting this link.

Participants

Study participants were from Western and non-Western backgrounds and varied in cultural background, including teachers, students, and social entrepreneurs. A purposive sampling technique was used to choose participants with expertise or experience in social entrepreneurship education. There were twenty persons, ten from Western and ten from non-Western countries.

Data Collection

Data were acquired by semi-structured interviews, either in person or via video conference, depending on the location and participant's interest. Participants permitted the interviews to be filmed and then transcribed for analysis. Apart from the interviews, relevant documents like curricular guides, program descriptions, and instructional policies were checked to provide context and enhance the interview outcomes.

Data Analysis

The data underwent thematic analysis. Transcripts were tagged to highlight patterns and recurring themes regarding how social entrepreneurship may influence employment. The investigation was conducted in many phases, beginning with open coding to establish relationships between the first categories and then with axial coding. Selective coding was the penultimate phase, aiming to refine and connect the ideas into a cohesive narrative.

Ethical Considerations

The research followed moral standards throughout the investigation. Every participant gave informed permission and was assured of their right to discontinue the study at any point. Giving pseudonyms and closely maintaining all the data assisted participants in maintaining their anonymity and privacy. The relevant ethics committees of the partnering colleges approved the study.

Limitations

The investigation had a limited scope. First, resting too much on self-reported interview data might introduce bias as participants could have responded in line with social expectations. Second, the cross-cultural aspect of the research might have led to differences in the concepts covered, comprehended, and interpreted, affecting the results' comparability. Eventually, especially in non-Western regions, the small sample size might restrict the generalizability of the results. Notwithstanding these limitations, the study provides a perceptive analysis of how social entrepreneurship could raise graduate employability in many different cultural contexts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Other people have different opinions about the research's conclusions. These cover the essential connections between employment and social entrepreneurship, the need for social entrepreneurship to increase employability, and how much social entrepreneurship teaching depends on the cultural environment.

Theme 1. Social endeavor helping in the job search

The research claims that social business offers important life lessons, including handling challenges, inspiring new ideas, and being flexible, thereby raising people's value. This backs up recent studies demonstrating social business advantages not only for individuals but also for students in the competitive work market of today (Martin & Osberg, 2007; Peredo & McLean, 2006). Teaching students about social entrepreneurship gives them pertinent skills and a mission-driven mentality that helps them to be more flexible and competitive in many career environments, claims Rahim and Mohtar (2015) and Wahid et al. (2019).

People from the West and other cultures noted the need to understand social business before one begins a job hunt. While the people from Western civilizations commended how creative and market-driven social entrepreneurship is, the people from non-Western civilizations stressed how important it is to develop reasonable, community-based solutions to local problems. More customized teaching strategies considering how different people's social and economic situations vary based on their region.

Theme 2. Introducing social business in many different cultural settings

The success of social business learning is strongly influenced by cultural background. According to the study, the values of the area, economy, and social norms significantly affect social business taught and observed. Previous studies (Urban & Kujinga, 2017; Sullivan Mort et al., 2003) show that the success of social entrepreneurs largely depends on their ability to interact with the local economy and culture. That helps to explain this new discovery. The social entrepreneurship curriculum centers on three primary elements: the social context, entrepreneurial activities, and managerial techniques. Managerial tools are vital for the efficient functioning of socially oriented businesses, with the program's syllabus highlighting decision-making strategies throughout. These tools' practical application is crucial for successfully operating social enterprises (EL Halaissi et al., 2023). Many social entrepreneurship courses in the West, where originality and market-driven innovation are usually praised, educate people on how to think like entrepreneurs, improving their creativity and risk-taking possibilities.

Teaching social business, however, is more likely to focus on inspiring individuals to cooperate, be socially conscious, and meet immediate needs in environments other than the West. They draw attention to the fact that there is no one method to teach social business that will appeal to everyone. Schools should instead be aware of several cultures and change to fit the customs and values of the places they run from.

Theme 3: Connecting social business education with workforce preparedness

According to the research, psychology and the degree of support someone feels are two fundamental components of employment and social business education. Regular attendees said that their families, communities, companies, and other social media sites support their sense of increased strength and security. These products benefit students as they help them maintain their commercial operations and manage challenges, improving their value. Baluku et al. (2020) and Hassan et al. (2022) assert that social networks and human values influence the development of businesses.

The ability to welcome change and bounce back after a setback was also significant. This was especially true in non-Western settings, where social and financial volatility might hinder business growth. Teaching social business should thus include exercises that empower

students intellectually, especially in environments where their success may be more complex and challenged.

The debate over the subject reveals the problematic link between work and understanding social business. It underlines the necessity of social context and mental strength. The numbers show how social business may help new grads land better jobs. Still, the degree of success of this form of training depends on how well it fits the local business and cultural standards. Learning about social business and selecting a decent job mostly depends on how well students can accept mistakes and how many people are reachable for them. These discoveries emphasize the significance of educational institutions operating programs valuing various cultures and helping students grow mentally so they may manage challenging situations.

Proposal for Social Entrepreneurship in Schools

To teach social business in a way that respects other cultures, you need to know a lot about their beliefs, ways of life, and budgets. These tips will help you do it:

1. Learn the right skills for the job

The problems you teach should have something to do with the people, money, and nature in your area. Put in case studies, success stories, and examples that are unique to your area.

Including habits from the area: To make the tool more helpful and important, add common knowledge, native ways of doing business, and native ways of solving problems.

2. Getting involved in your neighborhood

Getting to know each other: Get people, companies, and organizations in the area to help with the learning. You can work together, get help, or have someone come in and talk.

Help your kids join groups in their neighborhood that work on real projects that improve their neighborhoods. They will work better and fit in better if they get help from people in the area.

3. Different ways to adapt training

How people learn has changed. Accept and get used to the different ways people learn from other places. It may be better for work and projects to be done by groups in collectivist countries. In countries that value

independence, people might need more encouragement to be creative and take the lead. If it makes sense, teach in the local language or accent so everyone can understand. People also stay true to their country when they do this.

4. Help teachers and workers get trained

If teachers learn to deal with people from different countries, they will be better at this. Being aware of the beliefs, habits, and ways of speaking that people there have is one way to do this. After that, you can talk about things in a fun way for the kids.

Others who live and work in the area and know the rules and problems of the community should be encouraged to join. They can give the kids more good ideas and valuable models.

5. Tools that are custom-made for you

Set up ways for kids to get help from local businesses or community leaders who can give them advice that works for them and their culture.

Help kids from all walks of life and income levels learn how to deal with stress and stay strong in classes that are just right for them.

6. Learning about the ideals of the country

Morals and social norms from the area should be taught in the lessons. One way to do this in places that value family and society is to stress social businesses that help everyone, not just yourself. Make sure that the projects and activities you plan consider national rules and customs so that you do not upset or hurt people who follow them.

7. A Look Back and an Answer

When you make tests, culture should be taken into account. One way for students to show what they know besides regular tests is to do projects or give talks about things that are important to them. Make a way for kids and community members to comment on the event. This will keep it functional and aware of other countries.

8. Getting together with businesses in the area

Through cooperative networks, businesses, NGOs, and government bodies in the area can help with the project. These connections could help make sure that the education meets the needs of the area, provide

resources, and open up project opportunities in the real world.

Get your local government to pass laws that support social business education and are sensitive to different cultures. This will ensure that the idea is taken seriously and backed by the government. If you want to understand how the program works fully, you should use important measures and talk to partners in the area during the review.

If the review shows that the program needs to be changed, you should always do so. This will keep it in line with social and cultural needs. This subject is more valuable and important for all students if it is taught in a way that considers different cultures.

Proposal On Young Learners' Education

If we are to teach social business properly, children must be engaged, encouraged to think critically, and shown how the principles may be used in the real world. As they engage in public service projects, students apply classroom knowledge to tackle issues in the real world. This clarifies how difficult it is to launch and operate a social enterprise for students.

1. Service Learning

Set up school-day service projects whereby students could learn about societal issues and work out solutions. This would benefit the area and provide real-world practice opportunities. Case studies represent some ideas for problem-based learning (PBL). Read about social enterprises, both successful and unsuccessful, to learn about various approaches, difficulties, and results. Reading and discussing these stories lets people learn more about many facets of social business.

2. Examination of a situation

Children should be exposed to complex societal concerns and challenged to consider original solutions. This encourages kids to be creative and assists in their perspective on things.

3. Collective Learning

Students from many backgrounds should collaborate to develop ideas for social businesses under team projects. Cooperation operates like a real-life social business, lets individuals see things from several sides, and improves problem-solving ability. Using presentations, conversations, or classroom instruction, students should be able to impart knowledge to one another. If this is

applied, children will learn more and be better communicators and leaders.

4. Speaking and mentoring others

Students should be connected with social entrepreneurs who have been in business for some time so they may benefit from comments, advice, and real-life case studies. Having someone to support you makes using what you have learned more natural. Those running social companies, NGOs, or community improvement projects should be invited to share their challenges and successes. These presentations might inspire learners and impart some helpful knowledge.

5. Design Thought and Empathy Seminars

Teach kids to determine what others need by modeling design thinking concepts. In workshops, they may test ideas, create models, learn about various points of view, identify issues, and develop answers.

6. Rapid prototyping

Instruct your children to jot down their social cause commercial ideas rapidly. They may modify constantly as this approach lets them visualize their ideas and get comments immediately. Simulation tools and role-playing games let students operate an online social enterprise as part of a business exercise. This helps individuals to learn without risk how to manage money, operate a company, and make decisions. Just as social entrepreneurs collaborate in real life, students may improve their sales of ideas, involvement of stakeholders, and creation of partnerships using roleplaying games.

7. Changing the classroom environment

Give children books, movies, or internet activities to complete before class. Allowing students to communicate, solve issues, and apply what they have acquired in class helps to make learning more enjoyable and centered on them. The class should include group discussions, debates, and problemsolving exercises to help students closely consider the concepts of social business and their applications.

8. Sharing narratives and considering ideas

Students should share their own life stories or bring in the tales of social entrepreneurs to enable others to grasp concepts and act upon them. Stories enable individuals to relate to and grasp more general concepts. An excellent suggestion is to keep a notebook in which they

record their knowledge, challenges, and how those things connect to social business. When you consider something, you develop personally and learn more about it.

9. Pursues and contests

Ideas for Social Entrepreneurs: Organize events or participate in ones where students could develop and present their company concepts. This intensifies competitiveness and drives students to improve their ideas. During hackathons, student teams ought to cooperate to address societal issues. They must be fast in coming up with fresh ideas. People may be fast thinkers, creative, and cooperative in this sense.

10. Combine offline and online pursuits

Along with what you're doing in class, use websites, movies, and online papers to maximize your education. One may easily adjust the learning rate; blended learning suits everyone.

11. E-learning and massive open online courses (MOOCs)

Use MOOCs and other e-learning materials targeted for social business. Tools will let students observe objects from around the world and help them. Create games like operating a social company to help children learn as they play, transforming educational games into games. Learning using games may be more fascinating and enjoyable. Point or badge systems reward students for completing assignments, attending meetings, or reaching project objectives. More individuals might be eager and wish to participate.

12. The Instruction in Criticism

Relating ethically. Please discuss with your children how social business shapes their moral compass. Discuss issues including the environment, fairness, and justice. This allows people to think critically and increases their responsibility. The Socratic Method will help students to consider their opinions, values, and the results of their choices in social business. This helps you to reflect on your principles and want further thorough research.

If these approaches to instruction are correctly applied, they may be entertaining and beneficial. They can also enable students to be outstanding social entrepreneurs who can address challenging societal issues.

CONCLUSION

Society is experiencing significant changes, and business is gradually occupying center stage. College students should learn self-efficacy, persistence, and how to accept support from friends and relatives that can help them find jobs. Giving youngsters the chance to learn about social entrepreneurship helps everyone in general and gives them valuable skills. Researchers painstakingly interviewed people worldwide for their study. They claimed that participating in social business initiatives increases people's resilience and intelligence, which helps them get employment. Why should colleges teach social business? It helps to solve societal issues and gets people ready for the workforce. This study on social business emphasizes the need to consider and teach in ways sensitive to diverse cultures. Including cultural topics in the curriculum ensures that every student might absorb and behave correctly. Culturally aware teachers take into account the diverse backgrounds of their students. This increases the entertainment value and benefits of classroom learning. It also promotes new ideas that are good for the surroundings and people. It shows how considering culture and social business may help schools reach their more ambitious, long-term goals by focusing on what they now need. Fair and practical systems are reachable if educational institutions accept the ideas of social businesses and mix teaching strategies with cultural surroundings. As long as we can view things from many sides and meet the needs of a global society, new ideas and educational advancement will be outstanding. Should they achieve all of these goals, they will be ready for their jobs and ready to assist in environmental preservation.

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